

Agricultural University of Athens
Agricultural Economics and Development
Laboratory of Informatics

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Intelligent Digital Ecosystem for European Universities

Transforming Access to Excellence with Successful Alliances of Higher Education in Digital Agriculture

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Presentation structure

- 1 Background
- 2 Partners
- 3 Objective
- 4 Methodology
- 5 Results
- 6 Conclusions

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Background

TALLHEDA is a Horizon Widera project that aims to build a new long-term Alliance for Digital Agriculture between agricultural **Higher Education Institutions (HEIs)** from two Widening countries, **Greece** and **Serbia**, with leading non-widening agricultural universities, and local and international stakeholders from **Belgium**.

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Background

Widening countries lag behind the European average in Research and Innovation investment and scientific excellence.

The domain of **Digital Agriculture** is one prominent example.

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) of widening countries, like **Greece** and **Serbia**, can play a central role in addressing this issue.

HEIs **need support** for achieving excellence in research and education in the Digital Agriculture domain.

HEIs in non-widening countries like **Belgium** have gained significant experience by establishing an ecosystem that fosters close collaboration among HEIs.

Partners

Three European universities partnered with other national and local actors in the agri-food domain, to form an alliance in the framework of the EU project TALLHEDA, in order to analyse the needs for reforming and updating our offered courses and programmes to further facilitate and promote Digital Agriculture education.

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Objective

Fostering **collaboration** and **innovation** in Digital Agriculture within HEIs across Europe, particularly in widening countries.

Establish a culture of **excellence** in Digital Agriculture education and research.

4

Methodology

With a view to identifying the reform needs of HEIs in the area of Digital Agriculture, a comprehensive **survey (questionnaire)** was developed through a systematic process.

01

Review of existing critical aspects related to Digital Agriculture education within HEIs

02

Setting clear objectives with the questionnaire

03

Stakeholder engagement

04

Developing the questionnaire

4

Methodology: Questionnaire

The questionnaire underwent **revisions** to

Methodology: Structure of the Questionnaire

TALLHEDA - Shaping the Future of Digital Agriculture Education: A Questionnaire for Higher Education Institutions

- Purpose of the Questionnaire
- Project Overview
- Confidentiality & Data Usage
- Legal Information
- Estimated Completion Time
- **Current Perceptions and Challenges**
 - A. Perceptions about Digital Agriculture
 - B. Course/Curriculum Update
 - C. Programme Integration
 - D. Research Capacity in Digital Agriculture
 - E. Resources for Digital Agriculture
 - F. Student Engagement
- **Approaches for Addressing the Integration Challenges**
- General Information of the Respondents

Results

❖ General Information of the Respondents

Country (%)

N = 50

	Belgium	Greece	Serbia
Country (%) N = 50	22	40	38

Gender (%)

N = 48

❖ General Information of the Respondents

Current position at the Higher Education Institute (%)

Age group (%)

N = 49

❖ **Current Perceptions and Challenges**

A. Perceptions about Digital Agriculture

The impact of Digital Agriculture on reinforcing or enhancing courses:

The overall impact is rated between "High" and "Very High", with the majority leaning towards **"Very High Impact"**.

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

B. Course/Curriculum Update

Frequency of reforming or updating the content of courses to introduce or modify existing topics (e.g., updated slides, discussion topics, case studies):

New topics

New Digital Agriculture topics

The majority of HEIs reformed or updated the content of courses and introduced new digital topics **within the last year**.

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

B. Course/Curriculum Update

Familiarity with integrating Digital Agriculture topics into courses:

Most professors feel **moderately comfortable** of integrating Digital Agriculture topics into their courses.

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

C. Programme Integration

The integration of Digital Agriculture topics across Bachelor or Master's programme:

Integration of Digital Agriculture topics (%)
N = 48

The extent of Bachelor or Master's programme align with the latest technological developments in the field of Digital Agriculture:

Extent (%)
N = 46

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

D. Research Capacity in Digital Agriculture

Agreement for the following statement: 'The HEI has a sufficient number of research initiatives and projects related to Digital Agriculture.':

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

E. Resources for Digital Agriculture

Adequacy of the following resources:

Educational Materials and Curriculum Resources (%)

N = 49

Technological Tools and Software (%)

N = 49

Laboratory and Field Equipment (%)

N = 48

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

E. Resources for Digital Agriculture

Adequacy of the following resources:

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

E. Resources for Digital Agriculture

Adequacy of the following resources:

❖ Current Perceptions and Challenges

F. Student Engagement

Interest in acquiring knowledge focusing on Digital Agriculture techniques and technologies:

Opportunities to engage in real-world projects or internships with industry partners in relation to Digital Agriculture:

The importance of: Infrastructure enhancements (laboratories, computing resources, field equipment), for advancing Digital Agriculture at HEI:

❖ Approaches for Addressing the Integration Challenges

The impact of establishing a Digital Agriculture Innovation Hub or Community of Practice, involving HEIs, local farmers, agribusinesses, community organizations, and policy makers in overcoming Digital Agriculture barriers at HEI:

Conclusions

- The findings of the questionnaire will be reported back to the stakeholders and are being used to inform **strategies** for advancing Digital Agriculture education in higher education settings.
- Insights into the reform needs of HEIs in the domain of Digital Agriculture, paving the way for targeted **improvements** and enhanced **collaboration** in this critical field.
- The overall **impact** of Digital Agriculture on reinforcing or enhancing courses is rated **between “High” and “Very High”**, with the majority leaning towards “Very High”.
- The majority of HEIs reformed or updated the content of courses and introduced new digital agriculture topics **within the last year**.
- Most professors feel **moderately comfortable** of integrating Digital Agriculture topics into their courses.
- The integration of Digital Agriculture topics across Bachelor or Master’s programme is characterized as **“Good”**.
- The adequacy of resources for Digital Agriculture is characterized **“Fair”**.
- Half of the professors answered that students show interest in acquiring knowledge focusing on Digital Agriculture techniques and technologies **“to some extent”**.
- The impact of establishing a Digital Agriculture Innovation Hub or Community of Practice is considered as **“High”**.

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Thank you for your attention

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